

Original Research

Transformational Leadership, Absorptive Capacity and Innovative Work Behaviour: Case Study in the Ghanaian Hospitality Industry

Michael Worlanyo Akotia, Dennis Yao Dzansi¹
Emanuel Kodzo Sakyi

Faculty of Management Sciences, Central University of Technology, Free State,
Bloemfontein, South Africa

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of transformational leadership on innovative work behaviour (IWB) among employees in Ghana's hospitality sector. It also explored how organizational and employee absorptive capacity (AC) moderates the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour. Data were randomly collected from 795 employees across star-rated hotels in the Volta Region of Ghana through structured questionnaires. The findings reveal that transformational leadership significantly impacts employees' innovative work behaviour. In addition, organizational and employee absorptive capacity significantly moderate the transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour relationship (albeit negatively for organizational absorptive capacity). Therefore, hospitality managers can exhibit higher levels of inspiration and support to their employees to generate innovative activities and outcomes. Also, firms can implement appropriate structures that foster knowledge exploration, acquisition and application at the employee level. This is because it enhances employee innovative work behaviour, especially in the presence of a transformational leadership style.

Keywords: Absorptive capacity, hospitality industry, innovative work behaviour, transformational leadership, organizational innovation.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: ddzansi@cut.ac.za

Introduction

In today's competitive business landscape, innovative work behaviour (IWB), which implies the ability of employees to generate, initiate and implement innovative ideas, has become critical for the competitive advantage of organizations (Almunthiri, Bani-Melhem, Mohd-Shamsudin & Raziq, 2024; Mensah, Shukla & Iqbal, 2023). Specifically, the continued growth in the global hospitality industry can be connected to innovation and creative activities to meet contemporary customers' ever-changing desires and expectations (Njoroge, Anderson & Mbura, 2020). Deri, Ari, Ragavan, Niber, Zaaize, Akazire, Anaba and Andaara (2023) contend that the fight against COVID-19 brought about innovation in hospitality operations fostered through an inspired hospitality workforce. Hu, Danso, Mensah and Addai (2020) state that because the world economy today is so innovation-driven, it has become obvious that innovation is among the most critical factors for business success and survival.

At the workplace, the ability or failure of employees to exhibit IWB can be associated with how leaders lead and manage the workforce (Saeed, Afsar, Shahjehan, & Shah, 2019). Therefore, leadership styles remain a critical factor influencing employee IWB (Afsar, Badir & Saeed, 2014; Saeed et al., 2019). Due to its features like inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration, the transformational leadership style is believed to be linked to IWB among employees (Koziol-Nadolna, 2020; Kee, Rahman & Tan, 2020). Transformational leadership is the leadership approach where leaders support, motivate and inspire employees to make innovative attempts and create change to help shape, grow and position the company for future success (Kee, Rahman & Tan, 2020). Xenikou (2017) highlights that transformational leaders cast a dynamic organizational vision necessary to change cultural values and reflect greater innovation.

Despite the potential benefits associated with effective leadership and innovation, the situation has not been thoroughly investigated, especially among service organizations, including hotels, as most innovation-related studies are conducted within the manufacturing industry (Martin-Rios & Ciobanu, 2019; Vuković, Damnjanović, Papić-Blagojević, Jošanov-Vrgović & Gagić, 2018). In the Ghanaian context, studies have been conducted on leadership styles and connections with employee work engagement (Agbozo, 2018) and employee productivity (Alhassan, Ibrahim, Fuseini, Issah, & Eliasu, 2014). Moreover, employee performance (Malcalm & Tamatey, 2017) did not occur in the hotel industry. However, the hotel industry is unique due to its strong customer orientation, product centricity, and internationalization focus, while it is also plagued by skills shortages, a lack of innovation, and ineffective leadership (International Labour Organization, 2020). For instance, the hotel sector's uniqueness is evident in how employee creativity (Slåtten & Mehmetoglu, 2015), proactive personality (Buil, Martínez & Matute, 2019) and knowledge sharing (Otair, Abualoush, Obeidat & Bataineh, 2022) impact the relationship between transformational leadership and IWB. Moreover, Hongyun, Adomako, Appiah-Twum, Akolgo, Iqbal and Spio-Kwofie (2019) added that crucial industry trends like greater diversification, increased demand for quality customer services and technology use, call for leadership and organizational innovation research in the hospitality industry.

As a result, the lack of clarity and attention on the relationship between transformational leadership and IWB and the moderating roles of organizational and employee absorptive capacity in the Ghanaian hospitality industry creates the research gap that this study sought to unearth. Therefore, this study examined the moderating effects of organizational and employee absorptive capacity on the relationship between transformational leadership and employee IWB in the Ghanaian hospitality industry. In line with the aim of the study, the specific objectives of the study were to (i) examine the impact of transformational leadership style on innovative work behaviour, (ii) examine the moderating effect of organizational absorptive capacity on the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour, and (iii) examine the moderating effect of employee absorptive capacity on the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour.

This study is significant because it shows that transformational leadership and employee absorptive capacity are fundamental in fostering innovative work behaviour in the hospitality industry. Therefore, the study reveals how leadership can be merged with individual and firm-level conditions to foster employee innovativeness. Practically, the study highlights how hospitality leaders can institute a clear and strong sense of corporate culture based on the principle of empowerment to guide employee behaviour and decision-making. Ghanaian hospitality managers can use this consolidative impact to help their employees learn and innovate. Hospitality managers can also focus on channelling attention towards improving technology to advance learning and changing old work patterns to promote sustained organizational changes and innovative attempts. These can build the confidence and capacity of hospitality employees to function in an increasingly complex, stressful and evolving work environment.

Literature Review

Theoretical framework

The foundational theory for the study is the Social Exchange Theory (SET). This theory posits that social behaviour results from an exchange process aiming to maximize benefits and minimize costs (Cook, 2015). It emphasizes the role of reciprocal relationships in shaping behaviour, whereby good interactions are reciprocated positively and vice versa (Yin, 2018). Therefore, in the organizational setting, SET is about workplace actors (such as supervisors) treating employees positively or negatively initiating actions (Cropanzano, Anthony, Daniels & Hall, 2017). This means managers may initiate positive actions like administering justice or providing employees with needed support, whereas negative actions might include abusive supervision, rudeness and victimization (Cropanzano et al., 2017; Yin, 2018). These workplace actions tend to shape employees' reactions. Hence, employees try to reciprocate with positive responses when the initiating actions are also positive, while they are bound to respond negatively when the initiating actions are undesirable.

Essentially, the SET is applied to this study because it helps understand how applying transformational leadership in the hospitality workplace might foster a positive exchange relationship with employees, encouraging them to engage in innovative behaviours. For instance, Yang (2010) revealed that social exchange at the hospitality workplace

promoted job satisfaction among workers and readiness to support each other. Meira and Hancer (2021) also used the SET to show that perceived organizational support leads to psychological empowerment and service-oriented organizational citizenship behaviour. The SET also helps to understand the underlying psychological and relational mechanisms that drive employees to reciprocate transformational leadership with innovative behaviour. In this regard, Li, Sanders and Frenkel (2012) applied the SET to show that hospitality industry leaders who provided service and voluntary assistance encouraged subordinates which positively impacted employees' job preparedness to support each other. The SET further helps explain how a workplace environment for learning, acquiring and applying new knowledge can intensify employee IWB.

Overall, based on the tenets of SET, the higher the application of transformational leadership and employee and organizational absorptive capacity, the higher the level of employee IWB. This means employees are prepared to showcase innovativeness because the hospitality firms first provided effective leadership and avenues to acquire and apply new knowledge. Therefore, in situations where the leadership is not transformational or ineffective, employees are bound to respond by showing a lackadaisical attitude towards pursuing IWB. Thus, positive supervisor-employee exchanges within the hospitality environment foster employees' ability to generate, promote and utilize new ideas. These ideas can be used to solve work challenges to advance organizational success and sustainability.

Concept clarification

Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership is defined by its ability to inspire and motivate employees, encouraging them to exceed their usual performance (Nashon & Njoroge, 2019). Transformational leadership theory, developed by James MacGregor Burns and later expanded by Bernard Bass, focuses on how leaders can inspire and motivate followers to achieve higher levels of performance and foster a culture of innovation and change (Luo, Guchait, Lee & Madera, 2019; Tamer, Qais, Mujeeb & Valliappan, 2020). In connection to this research, the theory relates to transformational leadership's influence on employee innovative work behaviour. The theory provides the foundation for understanding how leadership behaviours influence employee outcomes. Thus, when leaders motivate, inspire, coach and mentor employees, they can feel empowered and be prepared to go beyond their required responsibilities and think creatively and innovatively to tackle challenging and emerging tasks. Research by Slåtten and Mehmetoglu (2015) and Otair et al. (2022) showed successful implementation of transformational leadership in the hospitality industry where it related to employee innovativeness whereas Buil, Martínez and Matute (2019) revealed that it improves proactive personality and employee performance.

Intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence transformational leaders. The intrinsic factors are idealized influence, inspirational drive, intellectual inspiration and individualized thought (Lee, 2018; Luo et al., 2019). These features explain how leaders demonstrate role model behaviour, inspire their followers to act ethically and morally, communicate a compelling vision to employees and encourage followers to be imaginative and creative

(Buil, Martínez & Matute, 2019; Lee, 2018; Raju & Phung, 2020). These intrinsic features represent the innate characteristics that transformational leaders exhibit to inspire followers to achieve organizational goals. The extrinsic factors are psychological empowerment, work autonomy, communication, and leader personality (Dias et al., 2022; Svendsen, Unterrainer & Jønsson, 2018). The extrinsic features describe the ability of leaders to generate positive behavioural results, delegate tasks, communicate effectively, coaching and mentorship (Dias et al., 2022; Mohammed et al., 2020; Varela, Gonzalez & Ochoa-Meza, 2020). These factors consider the external traits that transformational leaders showcase to create an enabling atmosphere for employees to help them grow.

Innovative work behaviour

Innovative work behaviour (IWB) is a construct that combines innovation with employee behaviour (Wijaya, 2018). The construct, derived from the broader field of organizational behaviour, relates to how individual and contextual factors combine to influence the generation, promotion and implementation of novel ideas within an organization (Bawuro et al., 2019; De Jong & Den Hartog, 2010). It provides a framework for understanding the mechanisms through which transformational leadership can stimulate innovative behaviours in employees. Theoretically, it elucidates the specific innovative actions of employees in response to leadership (Afsar, Badir & Saeed, 2014; Saeed et al., 2019). Thus, when organizational leaders create a conducive work environment, employees can focus on critical thinking to develop innovative solutions to tackle challenging and emerging tasks. Primarily, IWB starts with idea generation, where novel ideas may be created or generated due to work challenges, discontinuities and emerging trends. Afterwards, idea promotion transpires whereby people express willingness and preparation to support the formulated idea. This process involves building alliances to propagate the new idea and gain the required support for operationalization. Idea realization completes the IWB process as formulated ideas are tested and implemented to resolve challenges and foster work progress (Gülbahar, 2017; Janssen, 2000; Janssen, 2003).

Both individual and organizational factors determine employee IWB. The individual factors include personality traits like self-efficacy, proactive personality, employee absorptive capacity, work engagement and psychological capital (Enkel et al., 2017; Kadar et al., 2019; Keskin, 2020; Paloş et al., 2023). These individual factors explain one's level of persistence, devotion to work, propensity to take action, ability to assimilate and apply knowledge, and show hope, optimism, and resiliency to engage in IWB. Furthermore, the organizational factors that determine employee IWB are positive organizational climate, employee motivation, training and development and inclusive organizational structures (Andreeva et al., 2017; Chen & Cheng, 2021; Sethibe & Steyn, 2018; You et al., 2022). The organizational factors detail how a favourable work environment, capacity building, employee support, and participation in decision-making processes create a supportive atmosphere for employees to make innovative and groundbreaking attempts.

Absorptive capacity

Absorptive capacity, developed by Cohen and Levinthal (1990), refers to the ability of an organization or individual to recognize, assimilate and apply new knowledge (Huang et al., 2015). Thus, absorptive capacity denotes the ability of firms to gain new knowledge and apply the knowledge to profitable means. For Cohen and Levinthal (1990), this knowledge acquisition heavily depends on organizations' research and development efforts. However, Zahra and George (2002) criticized Cohen and Levinthal's (1990) focus on research and development and introduced two dimensions of absorptive capacities: potential absorptive capacity and realized absorptive capacity. Potential absorptive capacity relates to accommodating abilities of firms to receive and integrate external knowledge, while realized absorptive capacity sums up the ability of firms to transform and exploit acquired information and knowledge (Zahra & George, 2002; Müller, Buliga & Voigt, 2021).

Furthermore, Todorova and Durisin (2007) contested the position of Zahra and George (2002) and reintroduced the original definition of Cohen and Levinthal (1990) because the difference between potential absorptive capacity and realized absorptive capacity was blurred. Therefore, in analyzing the conceptualization of absorptive capacity, it is established that Cohen and Levinthal (1990), together with Todorova and Durisin (2007), conceptualized the idea of focusing on individual employees (Enkel et al., 2017). On the contrary, Zahra and George (2002) believed that absorptive capacity should primarily be conceptualized at the organizational level (Müller, Buliga & Voigt, 2021).

As a result, absorptive capacity is treated as individual absorptive capacity and organizational absorptive capacity. For this study, absorptive capacity is incorporated to explain the moderating roles of employee and organizational absorptive capacity in the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour. This means absorptive capacity tries to enlighten how the ability to assimilate and utilize knowledge enhances or strengthens the impact of leadership on employee innovative attempts.

Hypotheses development

Transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour

Transformational leadership, characterized by inspirational motivation, dedicated support to followers and intellectual stimulation, can potentially influence employee IWB (Slåtten & Mehmetoglu, 2015). Research by Kee, Rahman and Tan (2020) indicated that transformational leadership strongly impacts innovation. Similar outcomes have also been identified by Koziol-Nadolna (2020), who shows that transformational leadership is connected with organizational innovation in a positive and significant way. Li et al. (2020) further indicate that transformational leadership improves employee green creativity significantly. These pieces of evidence suggest that transformational leadership can encourage employees to establish trust and progressively assist in developing an inventive environment. Based on its reassuring features, transformational leadership supports employees' new ideas and encourages them to think outside the box. Therefore, due to the above interrelationships, the study hypothesizes that:

H₁: Transformational leadership style significantly influences innovative work behaviour.

The moderating role of absorptive capacity

The absorptive capacity that captures the integration and utilization of knowledge can improve firm performance (Qian & Jung, 2017). Absorptive capacity, either at the employee or organizational level, is believed to shape how leadership impacts IWB among employees (Qi, Jia & Zou, 2021; Yuliza, Muafi & Wahyuningsih, 2024). This denotes that employees' or organizations' ability to recognize, assimilate and apply new knowledge can strengthen how leadership, such as transformational leadership, influences employee IWB. In the case of the moderating role of employee absorptive capacity, research has revealed that individual absorptive capacity positively moderates the relationship between team internal social capital and taking charge (Chen et al., 2023). Team internal social capital represents the team's ability to acquire information and resources, and this is facilitated by authentic leadership, also driven by openness and inclusion. Therefore, employees who can assimilate and apply new knowledge enhance their ability to take charge, overcome high-power distance and act innovatively. Similarly, Elbaz, Agag and Alkathiri (2018) found that employee absorptive capacity moderates the relationship between knowledge received and innovative performance. Knowledge acquired is shaped by employees' leadership, motivational and opportunity-seeking abilities, and these are traits exhibited by transformational leaders.

Moreover, Chang et al. (2018) showed that unit-level absorptive capacity positively and significantly moderated the link between transformational leadership and unit innovative performance. Also, Otair et al. (2022) found that absorptive capacity positively moderates transformational leadership and empowers knowledge-sharing and innovation relationships. Similarly, Yuliza, Muafi and Wahyuningsih (2024) found that absorptive capacity strengthens the influence of digital leadership on innovation performance where digital leadership was conceptualized as a combination of transformational leadership style and digital technology. These findings demonstrate that higher levels of absorptive capacity translate to a stronger relationship between transformational leadership and employee IWB. Conversely, low-level information acquisition and application decreases the link between transformational leadership style and IWB. It is therefore hypothesized that:

H₂: Organizational absorptive capacity significantly moderates the influence of transformational leadership style on innovative work behaviour.

H₃: Employee absorptive capacity significantly moderates the influence of transformational leadership style on innovative work behaviour.

Conceptual framework

The developed conceptual framework offers an integrated model that provides a robust basis for analyzing the dynamics of transformational leadership style and its impact on innovative work behaviour within the context of absorptive capacity in the Ghanaian hospitality industry. Figure 1 depicts the hypothesized relationships among the variables.

Figure 1. The conceptual framework

Firstly, the framework suggests that hospitality organizations adopt a transformational leadership style at the workplace, employees can exhibit positive outcomes such as IWB. Thus, the high-level inspiration linked to the transformational leadership style creates a culture of innovativeness in work behaviours that permeates the workplace (Koziol-Nadolna, 2020; Li et al., 2020). In addition, the developed framework illustrates that the ability of employees and organizations to acquire, transform and apply new knowledge plays a moderating role and strengthens the relationship between transformational leadership and IWB (Chang et al., 2018; Otair et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research design, population and sampling

The research used the cross-sectional survey design to address transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour within the context of absorptive capacity in the Ghanaian hotel sector. The cross-sectional survey design was used because the study sought to gather data from a large sample size within a specific period to assess opinions (Setia, 2016) regarding transformational leadership and employee IWB. The study population comprised 30 star-rated hotels in the Volta Region of Ghana. Overall, 810 structured questionnaires were randomly distributed to hotel workers, including managers, supervisors and junior-level employees. Employees were sampled from all levels to gain a comprehensive data on the viewpoints of workers across all ranks. Moreover, simple random sampling was used to ensure that each unit in the population had equal chance of selection to yield representativeness and accuracy of estimations (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). Seven hundred ninety-five (795) questionnaires were filled correctly and retrieved, representing a 98.15% response rate. Data collection was done by modifying existing questionnaires to measure the key constructs of the study.

Measures

Transformational leadership: This construct comprised 20 items adapted from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) developed by Bass & Avolio (1997). This instrument was used because it is a validated tool for measuring transformational leadership style with strong evidence for construct validity and reliability (Batista-Foguet, Esteve & van Witteloostuijn, 2021). This measure used the 7-point Likert Scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). This construct was used to determine whether the leadership style in the Ghanaian hospitality workplace was transformational and promoted motivational inspiration, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. Examples of items include 'leaders inspire workers with power in this hotel', 'leadership in this hotel emphasizes a desirable vision', 'I feel motivated by the leadership style of this hotel', 'I am challenged to deliver extraordinary results', and 'I see that leadership in this hotel focuses on coaching/mentoring'.

Innovative work behaviour: This construct comprised 11 items adapted from the Innovative Working Behaviour Questionnaire developed by Janssen (2003). This tool was used because it has widely been applied as a valid and reliable instrument in research on employee innovativeness (Messmann & Mulder, 2012). This measure used the 7-point Likert Scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). This construct was used to determine how Ghanaian hospitality employees are inspired to generate, promote and apply novel ideas within the workplace. Examples of items include 'I consider myself to be a creative/innovative person', 'I look out for new working methods, techniques or instruments to solve problems', 'I can mobilize support for innovative ideas', 'I give my approval to innovative ideas' and 'I can transform innovative ideas into useful applications'.

Absorptive capacity: This construct comprised 14 items adapted from the Absorptive Capacity Scale designed by Flatten et al. (2011). Questions 1-10 focused on organizational absorptive capacity, whereas questions 11-14 concentrated on employee absorptive capacity. This instrument was used since it has been proven and validated in different organizational contexts (Engelman, Fracasso, Schmidt & Muller, 2016). This measure used the 7-point Likert Scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). This construct was used to determine how Ghanaian hospitality firms and employees can recognize, assimilate and apply new knowledge for organizational success. Examples of items include 'the hotel searches for relevant information concerning our industry daily', 'hotel management emphasizes inter-departmental support to solve problems', 'there is a quick information flow in this hotel where information from one department is shared promptly with all departments', 'employees in this hotel can grasp new knowledge and make it available when needed' and 'employees in this hotel can apply new knowledge in their practical work'.

Data analysis

Data analysis was done using SPSS Version 27 and Smart PLS Version 4. Specifically, SPSS Version 27 was used to generate descriptive statistics regarding the profile of respondents, whilst Smart PLS Version 4 was used to conduct Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) analysis to test the formulated research

hypotheses. Also, Smart PLS was incorporated because it excels in analyzing path models like moderation analysis compared to SPSS (Duryadi & Tangerang, 2024). In the research process for the PLS-SEM analysis, reliability and validity issues were addressed while their threats were minimized in several ways. Reliability threats were addressed by minimizing sampling error and scoring variability (Clark et al., 2021; Schindler, 2022). Sampling error was minimized by using a random sampling technique to increase the likelihood of obtaining a representative sample while the sample size was also adequate. Scoring variability was lessened by developing clear scoring guidelines and providing training to enumerators involved in data collection and coding.

Construct validity was enhanced by conducting a thorough literature review to select valid measurement instruments and using multiple indicators for each construct to improve quality (Clark & Watson, 2019). Also, measurement validity was achieved using established and validated measurement scales and convergent and discriminant validity assessments (Lac, 2016). Therefore, threats to reliability and validity were minimized through careful study design, rigorous measurement procedures, and appropriate data analysis techniques to enhance the quality and trustworthiness of the research.

Results and Discussion

Respondents' profile

The socio-demographic features assessed include gender, age, education, monthly salary and work experience. As shown in Table 1, 47.8% were males and 52.2% were females. Regarding respondents' age, the majority were between 36 and 40 (34.3%). This was followed by those aged 31-35, constituting 33.3% of the results. Also, 22.3% of respondents were under 30 years old, whilst 6.3% were in the 41-45 age range. Only 3.8% of respondents were more than 45 years old. The study further proved that 37.5% of respondents had obtained a bachelor's degree/advanced diploma. Interestingly, 31.6% have other qualifications that were not captured as part of the categories in this study. This was followed by those with an advanced diploma certificate, which comprised 24.9%. Moreover, 3.3% and 2.8% of respondents have master's/postgraduate diploma certificates and doctorate degrees, respectively. Regarding monthly salary, most respondents receive salaries below 1,000 Cedis per month (34.6%). This was followed by those who earned between 1,000 and 2,000 Cedis (31.1%). In addition, 14.3% earned 3,001 to 4,000 Cedis, whilst 12.5% earned 2,001 and 3,000 Cedis. Only 7.5% earn above 4,000 Cedis.

Furthermore, Table 1 indicates that most respondents worked in their respective hotels' sales/marketing sections (20.3%), followed by those in the catering sections (19.9%). 19.2% worked with housekeeping units, whilst 11.4% were stationed at the front office. Also, 8.7% work in the accounts sections of their hotels, whilst 7.5% form part of the HR unit. Again, 6.8% worked under security, whilst the remaining 6.2% worked with maintenance. Lastly, work experience showed that most respondents have worked below five years, representing 88.4%. However, only 5.0% have worked with their respective hotels between 6-10 years, followed by those with 16-20 years (2.5%). More so, 2.1% have been with their hotels for 11-15 years, whereas only 1.9% have worked with their hotels for over 20 years. These figures, therefore, demonstrate that most of the

respondents were females who were 40 years old or below and had reasonably good educational levels. Also, most hotel workers receive a monthly salary below 4,000 Cedis, while the length of service among respondents was generally low. These imply that hospitality leaders can motivate their employees, including improved remuneration for employees so they can stay longer at their jobs and showcase innovative behaviours to solve work challenges.

Table 1. Profile of respondents

Characteristics	Scale	N=795	%
Gender	Male	380	47.8
	Female	415	52.2
Age	Under 30 years	177	22.3
	31 – 35 years	265	33.3
	36 – 40 years	273	34.3
	41 – 45 years	50	6.3
	Over 45 years	30	3.8
Highest educational level	Diploma Advanced Certificate	198	24.9
	Bachelors' Degree/Advanced Diploma	298	37.5
	Masters Postgraduate Diploma	26	3.3
	Doctor's Degree	22	2.8
	Other	251	31.6
Monthly salary	Below 1,000 Cedis	275	34.6
	1,000-2,000 Cedis	247	31.1
	2,001-3000 Cedis	99	12.5
	3,001-4,000 Cedis	114	14.3
	Above 4,000 Cedis	60	7.5
Department	Housekeeping	153	19.2
	Front office	91	11.4
	Catering	158	19.9
	Sales/Marketing	161	20.3
	HR	60	7.5
	Accounts	69	8.7
	Maintenance	49	6.2
	Security	54	6.8
Work experience	Below 5 years	703	88.4
	6-10 years	40	5.0
	11-15 years	17	2.1
	16-20 years	20	2.5
	Over 20 years	15	1.9

PLS-SEM analysis

SMART PLS software was used to specify the SEM to test the research hypotheses. Model evaluation was made in two stages: measurement model and structural model (see Table 2). The measurement model was first evaluated to check the quality dimensions of

the inner model in terms of reliability, validity and collinearity statistics. After confirmation of the adequacy of the measurement model, the structural model was evaluated for significance (Hair, 2022).

Table 2. The two-stage PLS-SEM evaluation criteria

Model	Evaluations	Criteria	Reference
Measurement Model	Reliability – Cronbach's Alpha	≥ 0.7	(Hair, 2022)
	Reliability-Rho_a	≥ 0.7	
	Composite reliability	≥ 0.7	
	Convergent validity - Average variance extracted	> 0.5	
	Discriminant validity -HTMT ratio	< 1	
	Common method bias-Inner VIF	< 5	
Structural Model	Indicator reliability	Indicator loading > 0.7 ; $p \leq 0.05$	(Benitez et al., 2020)
	Coefficients and effect size	Unstandardized beta f^2 : Effect size values above 0.35 = strong, 0.15 = moderate, and 0.02 = weak	
	Coefficient of determination	R^2 : Results above 0.67 (Substantial), 0.33 (Moderate) and 0.19 (Weak)	

Measurement Model

The measurement model checked the quality dimensions of the inner model in terms of reliability, validity, discriminant validity and common method bias. Table 3 shows satisfactory reliability results (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7 ; Rho_a > 0.7). Composite reliabilities for the constructs are also satisfactory (rho_c > 0.7), while convergent validity is considered adequate for all the respective constructs. Again, based on the recommendations of Hair et al. (2022), there is no threat of discriminant validity for the constructs formed with their respective indicators (HTMT ratio > 0.5). Table 3 further indicates the absence of threats of common method bias in the estimated model (Inner VIF scores < 5). These findings demonstrate that the measurement model can progress to the structural stage.

Table 3. Reliability, Validity, Discriminant Validity and Common Method Bias

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Transformational leadership (TL)	0.893	0.929	0.915	0.609
Innovative work behaviour (IWB)	0.950	0.959	0.962	0.834
Organizational absorptive capacity (OAC)	0.893	0.953	0.915	0.687
Employee absorptive capacity (EAC)	0.897	0.952	0.928	0.763
Discriminant Validity				HTMT Ratio
Innovative work behaviour <-> Employee absorptive capacity				0.706
Organizational absorptive capacity <-> Employee absorptive capacity				0.797
Organizational absorptive capacity <-> Innovative work behaviour				0.623
Transformational leadership <-> Employee absorptive capacity				0.542
Transformational leadership <-> Innovative work behaviour				0.609
Transformational leadership <-> Organizational absorptive capacity				0.633
Common Method Bias				Inner VIF
Employee absorptive capacity -> Innovative work behavior				2.636
Organizational absorptive capacity -> Innovative work behaviour				2.977
Transformational leadership -> Innovative work behaviour				1.655
Organizational absorptive capacity x Transformational leadership -> Innovative work behavior				3.157
Employee absorptive capacity x Transformational leadership -> Innovative work behavior				3.148

Structural Model

The structural model evaluated the structural relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables using path coefficients and their level of significance (Benitez et al., 2020; Hair, 2022). Table 4 illustrates the indicator reliability, highlighting factor loadings within the range of 0.640 and 0.977 after iteration. These indicators are statistically significant (p values < 0.05).

Table 4. Indicator Loading

	Indicator	T statistics	P values
AC1 <- Organizational absorptive capacity	0.912	178.293	0.000
AC10 <- Employee absorptive capacity	0.937	217.491	0.000
AC11 <- Employee absorptive capacity	0.932	112.801	0.000
AC12 <- Employee absorptive capacity	0.793	42.880	0.000
AC2 <- Organizational absorptive capacity	0.940	168.309	0.000
AC4 <- Organizational absorptive capacity	0.768	38.434	0.000
AC5 <- Organizational absorptive capacity	0.658	24.846	0.000
AC8 <- Organizational absorptive capacity	0.836	61.251	0.000
AC9 <- Employee absorptive capacity	0.824	45.656	0.000
IWB1 <- Innovative work behaviour	0.926	189.496	0.000
IWB2 <- Innovative work behaviour	0.926	272.627	0.000
IWB3 <- Innovative work behaviour	0.977	234.718	0.000
IWB4 <- Innovative work behaviour	0.921	136.407	0.000
IWB5 <- Innovative work behaviour	0.808	68.482	0.000
TL1 <- Transformational leadership	0.846	73.398	0.000
TL15 <- Transformational leadership	0.640	20.447	0.000
TL16 <- Transformational leadership	0.681	7.358	0.000
TL2 <- Transformational leadership	0.865	80.386	0.000
TL3 <- Transformational leadership	0.857	59.455	0.000
TL4 <- Transformational leadership	0.833	59.263	0.000
TL5 <- Transformational leadership	0.705	31.495	0.000

The findings in Table 5 highlight the path coefficients of the direct and moderation effects and the coefficient of determination. The coefficient of determination shows that changes in transformational leadership amid the intervening effect of employee and organizational absorptive capacity account for a 58.6% improvement in employee innovative work behaviour (Beta=0.586).

Concerning the hypotheses, the results first reveal that transformational leadership significantly predicts innovative work behaviour (Beta=0.325; $p=0.000$; $p<0.05$; $f^2=0.154$) with a small effect size. Furthermore, the moderation analysis indicated that organizational absorptive capacity moderates significantly (albeit negatively) the predictive relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour (Beta=-0.125; $p=0.007$; $p<0.05$) with a weak effect ($f^2=0.017$). Employee absorptive capacity also significantly and positively moderates the predictive relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour (Beta=0.185; $p=0.002$; $p<0.05$) with a small effect size ($f^2=0.032$).

Table 5. Structural Model Path Coefficients

Hypothesis	Path Analysis	Beta	f-square	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
	Direct Path					
H ₁	TL -> IWB	0.325	0.154	11.011	0.000	Supported
	Moderation					
H ₂	OAC x TL -> IWB	-0.125	0.017	2.479	0.007	Supported
H ₃	EAC x TL -> IWB	0.185	0.032	2.942	0.002	Supported
Co-efficient of Determination						
	IWB	R ² = 0.586		R ² adjusted = 0.583		

Note: TL = Transformational Leadership; IWB = Innovative Work Behaviour; OAC = Organizational Absorptive Capacity; and EAC = Employee Absorptive Capacity

The findings support the hypothesis (H1) that transformational leadership style significantly influences innovative work behaviour. This finding means that transformational leadership style proves to be a key predictor of innovative work behaviour among hotel workers in Ghana. Thus, when hotel managers exhibit higher levels of inspiration and support to their employees, the staff members can generate innovative activities. The role of transformational leadership style in significantly predicting innovative work behaviour, as revealed from this study, is confirmed in previous research. Studies by Kee, Rahman and Tan (2020), Koziol-Nadolna (2020) and Li et al. (2020) demonstrated that transformational leadership and innovative behaviour have a good relationship. Employees are encouraged by the leadership style that dwells on delegation and inspiration to have a compelling vision, work in teams and bring new ideas that create innovation.

Also, the results support the hypothesis (H2) that organizational absorptive capacity significantly moderates the influence of transformational leadership style on innovative work behaviour. This finding implies that the ability of hoteliers to acquire, integrate and utilize knowledge can impact the relationship between transformational leadership style and innovative work behaviour within the Ghanaian hotel sector. The significant moderation effect supports that of Yuliza, Muafi and Wahyuningsih (2024), who found that absorptive capacity moderates the relationship between digital leadership and innovation performance. As stated earlier, digital leadership combines a transformational leadership style and digital technology. Nevertheless, the negative (inverse) moderating effect opposes findings from previous studies. Here, researchers like Chang et al. (2018) and Otair et al. (2022) found a positive moderating role of organizational-level absorptive capacity in relationships involving attributes related to transformational leadership and employees' innovative work behaviour.

Lastly, the findings support the hypothesis (H3) that employee absorptive capacity significantly moderates the influence of transformational leadership style on innovative work behaviour. This implies that the capacity of hotel workers to recognize, assimilate and apply knowledge reinforces the relationship between transformational leadership style and innovative work behaviour within the Ghanaian hotel sector. This result is similar to the findings of earlier scholars. For instance, Chen et al. (2023) found that individual absorptive capacity significantly moderates the relationship between team internal social capital and taking charge. Team internal social capital is facilitated by authentic leadership and driven by openness and inclusion. Therefore, employees who can assimilate and apply new knowledge enhance their ability to take charge, overcome high-power distance and act innovatively. Similarly, Elbaz, Agag and Alkathiri (2018) found that employee absorptive capacity moderates the relationship between knowledge received and innovative performance. Knowledge received is shaped by employees' leadership, motivational and opportunity-seeking abilities, and these are traits exhibited by transformational leaders.

Figure 2. Structural Model

Conclusion

The heightened level of competition in the hospitality industry has forced operators to continue to review ways in which both firms and employees can contribute to organizational innovation. Therefore, this study adopted a unique approach to understanding transformational leadership in the context of absorptive capacity to influence employee innovative work behaviour. The study confirms that transformational leadership in the hotel industry significantly produces desirable outcomes on innovative work behaviour among hotel workers. Moreover, the study concludes that employee

absorptive capacity re-enforces the effect of transformational leadership on employee innovative work behaviour in the hotel industry. However, the interaction of organizational absorptive capacity with transformational leadership reduces the effect of transformational leadership on employee innovative work behaviour. Therefore, hospitality managers can exhibit higher levels of inspiration and support to their employees to generate innovative activities. Also, firms can implement appropriate structures that concentrate on fostering knowledge acquisition and application at the employee level because it heightens innovative work behaviour, especially in the presence of a transformational leadership style.

Implications

Managerial implications

Firstly, hotels in Ghana can adopt and implement a transformational leadership style in managing their business operations because it has been proven to improve employees' innovative work behaviour. This can be done by hotel managers demonstrating desired behavior and values from the top, building a culture of ownership among employees and promoting independence at the workplace. These inspire, empower and give employees the needed support to come up with creative and innovative ideas. Also, hotel managers can commit themselves to efficiently executing the aspects of transformational leadership indicators that reliably measure the construct. These practices include building trust among workers and their leaders, strategically framing problems by leaders in ways that make the problems solvable, leaders' capacity of support in tackling old situations in new ways, leaders inspiring workers with power, instilling pride among employees to work, leaders going beyond their interests for employees' interest and acting with integrity at all instances. Secondly, hotel management can support employees with research and capacity-building training to enhance their knowledge exploration, acquisition and utilization competence. Importantly, with these things in place, hotel employees can reciprocate favourably by going the extra mile, taking informed risks and making innovative attempts to solve work challenges. Furthermore, it is vital to highlight that the inverse moderating role of organizational absorptive capacity calls for hotel management to evaluate the conditions affecting firm-level knowledge acquisition and utilization to yield improved outcomes. These initiatives can help hotels improve their brand image, competitive positioning, and profit margins.

Policy implications

Hotel businesses can devise corporate-level policies to build their leadership and governance on the tenets of transformational leadership. For instance, transformational leadership can be adopted at the executive level to guide behavior, values and working culture. Resources, including budget, personnel, structures, systems and facilities, can be provided to ensure a working transformational leadership policy. All people occupying managerial positions can be trained extensively on how to translate ideas of transformational leadership into a working culture that could imbibe among all workers a sense of reciprocity and change in working behaviour. Hospitality firms can also institute a policy of regularly conducting internal audits and external benchmarking to improve absorptive capacity. These audits would help identify existing knowledge gaps

(for e.g., relating to new technology) and assess how effectively new information is integrated at both employee and organizational levels.

Theoretical contributions

First, the research contributes to the management and leadership theory by providing an integrated framework to promote organizational innovation, especially in the hospitality sector (Hongyun et al., 2019). Thus, this research confirms that transformational leadership style and employee absorptive capacity should be incorporated as building blocks to conceptualize organizational innovation within hospitality. Also, the research demonstrates that empowerment philosophy at the workplace may be beneficial in achieving employee IWB (Mohammed et al., 2020; Saeed et al., 2019). Thus, aspects of empowerment, such as coaching, autonomy, learning and development, which transformational leaders apply, can potentially result in higher levels of employee IWB. Moreover, the significant relationships of the research underscore the importance of Social Exchange Theory. This study advances the theory built on reciprocity because hotel employees are prepared to showcase innovativeness at the workplace in response to empowerment-type leadership and avenues to acquire, assimilate and apply new knowledge. Therefore, the social exchange theory, focusing on positive initiating actions like providing employees with needed support, can serve as a guide to shaping working relationships and exchanges at the hospitality workplace to help generate positive outcomes.

Research limitations

The study focused on a quantitative cross-sectional study, limiting the in-depth knowledge that could have been gained if the mixed research method had been adopted. Again, the study ignored other relevant contextual factors such as firm age, size, and location in their context.

Recommendations for future studies

Further studies could incorporate qualitative tools like in-depth interviews to do longitudinal mixed research to study transformational leadership and innovative work behavior in the hospitality industry of Ghana. The incorporation of qualitative tool could help understand employee sentiments about leadership and innovative work behaviour. Further studies could consider contextual factors such as firm age, location and size as possible moderating or controlled variables to examine their effect. New studies can also explore workplace conditions that relate to leadership like organisational justice and investigate how it impacts employee innovative work behavior among hospitality workers.

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References

- Afsar, B., Badir, Y. F., & Saeed, B. B. (2014). Transformational Leadership and Innovative Work Behaviour. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 114(8), 1270-1300.
- Agbozo, G. K., Owusu, I. S., Hoedoafia, M. A., & Atakorah, Y. B. (2017). The Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction: Evidence from the Banking Sector in Ghana. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(1), 12–18.
- Alhassan, Y., Ibrahim, O., Fuseini, M., Issah, G., & Eliasu, I. (2014). Assessing the Effects of Leadership Styles on Staff Productivity in Tamale Polytechnic, Ghana. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 2(9), 1-23.
- Almunthiri, O., Bani-Melhem, S., Mohd-Shamsudin, F., & Raziq, M. M. (2024). Fostering Innovative Behaviours of Public Sector Employees: The Potency of Innovation-Based HR Practices, Risk Propensity and Error Tolerance. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 37(2), 159-182.
- Andreeva, T., Vanhala, M., Sergeeva, A., Ritala, P., & Kianto, A. (2017). When the Fit between HR Practices Backfires: Exploring the Interaction Effects between Rewards for and Appraisal of Knowledge Behaviours on Innovation. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(3), 9-27.
- Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1997). *Full Range Leadership Development - Manual for the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire*. Redwood City, CA: Mindgarden Publishers.
- Batista-Foguet, J. M., Esteve, M., & van Witteloostuijn, A. (2021). Measuring Leadership: An Assessment of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. *PLoS ONE*, 16(7), e0254329.
- Bawuro, F., Shamsuddin, A., Wahab, E., & Usman, H. (2019). Mediating Role of Meaningful Work in the Relationship between Intrinsic Motivation and Innovative Work Behaviour. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 8(9), 2076- 2084.
- Benitez, J., Henseler, J., Castillo, A., & Schuberth, F. (2020). How to Perform and Report an Impactful Analysis Using Partial Least Squares: Guidelines for Confirmatory and Explanatory IS Research. *Information & Management*, 57(2), 103168.

- Buil, I., Martínez, E., & Matute, J. (2019). Transformational Leadership and Employee Performance: The Role of Identification, Engagement and Proactive Personality. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77, 64-75.
- Chang, Y., Chao, W., Chang, C., & Chi, H. (2018). Transformational Leadership Influence on Unit Performance. *Leadership & Organisation Development Journal*, 39(4), 554-571.
- Chen, G., Wang, J., Dong, Z., & Zhang, X. (2023). How Does Authentic Leadership Promote Taking Charge: The Mediating Effect of Team Social Capital and the Moderating Effect of Absorptive Capacity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13: 1046914.
- Chen, X., & Cheng, J. (2021). A Review of the Inclusive Leadership Research and its Prospects from the Vision of China. *Science Research Management*, 42, 174–181.
- Clark, L. A., & Watson, D. (2019). Constructing Validity: New Developments in Creating Objective Measuring Instruments. *Psychological Assessment*, 31(12), 1412-1427.
- Clark, T., Foster, L., Sloan, L., & Bryman, A. (2021). *Social Research Methods* (6th Edition). London: Oxford University Press.
- Cohen, W. M., & Levinthal, D. A. (1990). Absorptive Capacity: A New Perspective on Learning and Innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 35(1), 128-152.
- Cook, K. S. (2015). Exchange: Social. In: Wright, J. D. (Eds.). *International Encyclopaedia of the Social and Behavioural Sciences*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2022). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (6th Edition). Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Cropanzano, R., Anthony, E. L., Daniels, S. R., & Hall, A. V. (2017). Social Exchange Theory: A Critical Review with Theoretical Remedies. *Academy of Management Annals*, 11(1), 479-516.
- De Jong, J. P. J., & Den Hartog, D. N. (2010). Measuring Innovative Work Behaviour. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 19(1), 23-26.
- Deri, M. N., Ari Ragavan, N., Niber, A., Zaazie, P., Akazire, D. A., Anaba, M., & Andaara, D. (2023). COVID-19 Shock in the Hospitality Industry: Its Effect on Hotel Operations within the Bono Region of Ghana. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 14(3), 355-378.
- Dias, A. L., Pascoal, B., Pereira, L. F., & da Costa, R. L. (2022). Transformational Leadership Contributions for Employee Autonomy. *International Journal of Service Science Management Engineering and Technology*, 13(1), 1-21.

- Duryadi, M., & Tangerang, S.M. (2024). Processing, Analyzing and Testing Quantitative Research Hypotheses with Smartpls Software3. *Journal of Engineering, Electrical and Informatics*, 4(1), 31-55.
- Elbaz, A. M., Agag, G. M., & Alkathiri, N. A. (2018). How Ability, Motivation and Opportunity Influence Travel Agents Performance: The Moderating Role of Absorptive Capacity. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 22(1), 119-141.
- Engelman, R., Fracasso, E. M., Schmidt, S., & Muller, H. F. (2016). Absorptive Capacity: Adaptation and Validation of a Scale in South Brazilian Companies. *Biotechnology, Agronomy, Society and Environment*, 13, 235-247.
- Enkel, E., Heil, S., Hengstler, M., & Wirth, H. (2017). Exploratory and Exploitative Innovation: To What Extent do the Dimensions of Individual Level Absorptive Capacity Contribute? *Technovation*, 60-61, 29–38.
- Flatten, T., Engelen, A., Zahra, A., & Brettel, M. (2011). A Measure of Absorptive Capacity: Scale of Development and Validation. *European Management Journal*, 29, 98-116.
- Gülbahar, Y. (2017). A Theoretical Investigation on Innovative Work Behaviours and Fear of Failure. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management Inquiries*, 1(1), 40-59.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (3rd Edition). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Hongyun, T., Adomako, K. W., Appiah-Twum, F., Akolgo, I. G., Iqbal, S., & Spio-Kwofie, A. (2019) Adoption of Open innovation: Evidence from SMEs in the Ghanaian Hospitality Industry. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 7(7), 1238-1253.
- Hu, X., Danso, B. A., Mensah, I. A., & Addai, M. (2020). Does Innovation Type Influence Firm Performance? A Dilemma of Star-Rated Hotels in Ghana. *Sustainability*, 12: 9912.
- Huang, K., Lin, K., Wu, L., & Yu, P. (2015). Absorptive Capacity and Autonomous R&D Climate Roles in Firm Innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(1), 87-94.
- International Labour Organization (2020). Sector Skills Strategy: Tourism and Hospitality Sector. Accra: International Labour Organization.
- Janssen, O. (2000). Job Demands, Perceptions of Effort-Reward Fairness and Innovative Work Behaviour. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73(3), 287-302.

- Janssen, O. (2003). Innovative Behaviour and Job Involvement at the Price of Conflict and Less Satisfactory Relations with Co-Workers. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 76(3), 347-364.
- Kadar, N., Sandi, M. M., Eliyana, A., Kurniasari, D., & Kurniasari, D. (2019). Proactive Work Behavior and Innovative Work Behavior: Moderating Effect of Job Characteristics. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(6), 373-379.
- Kee, D. M. H., Rahman, N. A., & Tan, A. W. (2020). The Impact of Transformational Leadership and Team Innovation on Team Performance: Empirical Evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Management and Marketing Review*, 5(2), 99-106.
- Keskin, E. (2020). Relationships among Self-efficacy, Job Resourcefulness and Job Performance of Hotel Cooks in Cappadocia. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic Tourism*, 5(1), 17-27.
- Koziol-Nadolna, K. (2020). The Role of a Leader in Stimulating Innovation in an Organization. *Administrative Science*, 10(59), 1-18.
- Lac, A. (2016). Measurement Validity. In: Levesque, R. J. R (Eds.). *Encyclopedia of Adolescence*. Switzerland: Springer International, pp. 1-4.
- Lee, J. Y. (2018). The Effects of Job Characteristics on the Team Creativity of Distribution Companies: Moderating Effects of Transformational Leadership. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 5(4), 161-172.
- Li, W., Bhutto, T. A., Xuhui, W., Maitlo, Q., Zafar, A. U., & Ahmed B. N. (2020). Unlocking Employees' Green Creativity: The Effects of Green Transformational Leadership, Green Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 255, 120229.
- Li, X., Sanders, S. & Frenkel, S. (2012). How Leader-member Exchange, Work Engagement and HRM Consistency Explain Chinese Luxury Hotel Employees' Job Performance. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 31(4), 1059-1066.
- Luo, A., Guchait, P., Lee, L., & Madera, J. M. (2019). Transformational Leadership and Service Recovery Performance: The Mediating Effect of Emotional Labor and the Influence of Culture. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77(4), 31-39.
- Malcalm, E., & Tamatey, S. (2017). Examining Leadership Style on Employee Performance in the Public Sector of Ghana: A Case of Ghana Atomic Energy Commission. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(11), 343-361.
- Martin-Rios, C., & Ciobanu, T. (2019). Hospitality Innovation Strategies: An Analysis of Success Factors and Challenges. *Tourism Management*, 70, 218-229.

- Meira, J. V. d. S. & Hancer, M. (2021). Using the Social Exchange Theory to Explore the Employee-Organization Relationship in the Hospitality Industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 33(2), 670-692.
- Mensah, L. E., Shukla, S., & Iqbal, H. F. (2023). Green Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Innovative Behaviour: Reflection from Ghana. *IIMBG Journal of Sustainable Business and Innovation*, 1(1), 58-74.
- Messmann, G., & Mulder, R. H. (2012). Development of a Measurement Instrument for Innovative Work Behaviour as a Dynamic and Context-Bound Construct. *Human Resource Development International*, 15(1), 43-59.
- Mohammed, A., Abdul, R., Mohammed, A., Yaser, H., & Ali A. (2020). The Impact of Transformational Leadership and Psychological Empowerment on Organizational Citizenship Behaviours: A PLS-SEM Approach. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(9), 908-917.
- Müller, J. M., Buliga, O., & Voigt, K. I. (2021). The Role of Absorptive Capacity and Innovation Strategy in the Design of Industry 4.0 Business Models - A Comparison Between SMEs and Large Enterprises. *European Management Journal*, 39(3), 333-343.
- Nashon, O., & Njoroge, J. G. (2019). Effects of Leadership Styles on Employee Performance: Case of Technical University of Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 7(6), 115-132.
- Njoroge, M., Anderson, W., & Mbura, O. (2020). Innovation Strategy and Economic Sustainability in the Hospitality Industry. *The Bottom Line*, 32(4), 253-268.
- Otaif, M., Abualoush, S., Obeidat, A., & Bataineh, K. (2022). Improving Firm's Innovation Performance Through Transformation Leadership and Knowledge Sharing: The Moderating Role of Absorptive Capacity. Case Study in Jordan. *Information Science Letters*, 11(5), 1693-1709.
- Paloş, R., Samfira, E. M., Vîrgă, D., & Purić, D. (2023). The Core Self-Evaluations, Psychological Capital, and Academic Engagement: A Cross-National Mediation Model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14: 1189665.
- Qi, G., Jia, Y., & Zou, H. (2021). Is Institutional Pressure the Mother of Green Innovation? Examining the Moderating Effect of Absorptive Capacity. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, 123957.
- Qian, H., & Jung, H. (2017). Solving the Knowledge Filter Puzzle: Absorptive Capacity, Entrepreneurship and Regional Development. *Small Business Economics*, 48(1), 99-114.
- Raju, V., & Phung, S. P. (2020). Economic Dimensions of Blockchain Technology: In the Context of Extension of Cryptocurrencies. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 29-39.

- Saeed, B., Afsar, B., Shahjehan, A., & Shah, S. (2019). Does Transformational Leadership Foster Innovative Work Behavior? The Roles of Psychological Empowerment, Intrinsic Motivation, and Creative Process Engagement. *Economic Research*, 32(1), 254-281.
- Schindler, P. S. (2022). *Business Research Methods* (14th Edition). New York: McGraw Hill International Editions.
- Sethibe, T., & Steyn, R. (2018). The Mediating Effect of Organisational Climate on the Relationship between Leadership Styles and Their Components on Innovative Behaviour. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Emerging Economies*, 4(1), 22-32.
- Setia, M. S. (2016). Methodology Series Module 3: Cross-sectional Studies. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*, 61(3), 261-264.
- Slåtten, T., & Mehmetoglu, M. (2015) The Effects of Transformational Leadership and Perceived Creativity on Innovation Behavior in the Hospitality Industry. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism*, 14(2), 195-219.
- Svendsen, M., Unterrainer, C., & Jønsson, T. F. (2018). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Job Autonomy on Promotive and Prohibitive Voice: A Two-Wave Study. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 25(2), 171-183.
- Tamer, M., Qais, A., Mujeeb S., & Valliappan, R. (2020). Theory of Transformational Leadership towards Employee Performance as Sequence of Supply Chain Model: The Mediating Effect of Job Autonomy in Palestine Banks during COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 9(5), 256-263.
- Todorova, G., & Durisin, B. (2007). Absorptive Capacity: Valuing a Reconceptualization. *The Academy of Management Review*, 32(3), 774-786.
- Varela, D, Gonzalez, C., & Ochoa-Meza, G. (2020). Measuring Transformational Leadership Style and its Effectiveness on Virtual Work-teams in Mexico. *Revista Espacios*, 41(43), 113-128.
- Vuković, A. J., Damnjanović, J., Papić-Blagojević, N., Jošanov-Vrgović, N., & Gagić, S. (2018). Impact of Leadership on Innovation: Evidence from the Hotel Industry. *Management: Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies*, 23(3), 57-66.
- Wijaya, O. (2018). Effect of Leader-Member Exchange and Perceived Organizational Support on Innovative Work Behaviour of Star Rated Hotel Employees. *Journal of Applied Management*, 16(4), 574-585.
- Xenikou, A. (2017). Transformational Leadership, Transactional Contingent Reward, and Organisational Identification: The Mediating Effect of Perceived Innovation and Goal Culture Orientations. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8: 1754.

- Yang, J.-T. (2010). Antecedents and Consequences of Job Satisfaction in the Hotel Industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(4), 609-619.
- Yin, N. (2018). The Influencing Outcomes of Job Engagement: An Interpretation from the Social Exchange Theory. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 67(5), 873-889.
- You, Y., Hu, Z., Li, J., Wang, Y., & Xu, M. (2022). The Effect of Organizational Innovation Climate on Employee Innovative Behaviour: The Role of Psychological Ownership and Task Interdependence. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13: 856407.
- Yuliza, S., Muafi, M., & Wahyuningsih, S. H. (2024). The Impact of Digital Leadership and Innovative Behaviour on Innovation Performance: The Moderating Role of Absorptive Capacity. *Journal of System and Management Sciences*, 14(4), 252-268.
- Zahra, S., & George, G. (2002). Absorptive Capacity: A Review, Reconceptualization, and Extension. *Academy of Management Review*, 27(2), 185-203.

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